

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Planning of an Arabic language education program to improve speaking skills in the Modern Pondok al Barokah Nganjuk Indonesia

Moch. Zainul Arifin *, Achmad Patoni and Kojin

Islamic Education Management, Doctoral Program of UIN Ali Sayyid Ali Rahmatullah Tulungagung, Indonesia.

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the planning of the Arabic Language Education Program to improve speaking skills at Pondok Modern Al Barokah Nganjuk. This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach with case studies as its method. Data was collected through interviews, observation, and documentation. Data analysis was carried out repeatedly using data presentation and verification techniques, as well as checking the validity of the data through credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. The results of this study conclude that learning planning at Pondok Modern Al-Barokah Nganjuk involves developing quality teaching staff through training and further education and designing learning programs integrated into various activities with a practice-based learning approach (learning by doing).

Keywords: Learning Planning; Speaking Skills; Islamic Boarding School; Arabic Language Education Program; Learning by Doing.

1. Introduction

In the era of reform and digital which is currently underway, and in line with progress in various sectors, including the field of education, which began in 2003 with the ratification of Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, following Article 31 Paragraph 2 of the 1945 Constitution (Kholil Fathoni, M, 2005). Education and teaching have become essential needs for all individuals. Knowledge and culture can be passed on to the next generation through education. This is achieved through the teaching and learning process, which is an interaction between educators and students, under UUSPN No. 20 of 2003, which defines *learning* as interaction in the learning environment to achieve certain educational goals, as explained by Scunk that learning is an interaction that involves students and their context (teacher, material, and setting) (Leli Halimah, 2017).

In education, many problems must be faced, including curriculum, teaching staff, facilities, learning processes, students, the role of parents, society, and the educational environment. However, one of the most dominant aspects in the world of education is the role of the teacher because they have a major role in the success of the teaching and learning process in the classroom. As educators, teachers must act as directors and coaches of students toward achieving maximum educational goals.

One of the subjects that play an important role in instilling moral values is learning Arabic through memorizing vocabulary and conveying moral messages through *muthala'ah* stories in Arabic. Arabic language education aims to develop students' communication skills and understanding of Arabic to master and understand Arabic texts, including the holy Qur'an. The purpose of Arabic subjects is for students to understand, believe, and practice Islamic teachings conveyed in Arabic so that they become individuals who believe and fear Allah SWT (Ahmad Susanto, 2013).

* Corresponding author: Moch. Zainul Arifin; Email: mohzainul98@gmail.com

Arabic is also one of the foreign languages used in communication in Indonesia. In addition, Arabic is also the language of the Qur'an, which is a way of life for Muslims. This language has a high literary value and is highly valued. In the Arabic Language Education Program, management includes planning, organizing, controlling, and evaluating activities to achieve goals. Management principles in this context are universal, although they differ in their implementation in various fields. This shows that management principles apply in any context.

The importance of collaboration between Kyai (religious leaders) and ustadz (teachers) in managing Arabic learning is to ensure that educators have adequate knowledge in designing Arabic learning. Ideally, an educator not only has expertise in the field of study or subject matter but also masters Arabic so that the learning methods used can improve the quality of learning outcomes. If an educator does not have expertise in Arabic, it is necessary to involve other religious experts to develop learning optimally.

In the context of the Arabic Language Education Program, several stages can be classified as follows:

- Planning: The first stage in a job involves explanations related to achieving maximum results. Planning is the first step in determining a strategy to achieve optimal results from an action (Didin et al., 2006).
- Organization: It involves determining the function and structure of relationships within a goal. The organization aims to achieve the goals set by establishing staff and functions that focus on management responsibilities, both among staff and with leaders (Nanang Fatah, 2001).
- Execution: This is the main management function emphasizing the pattern of activities involving people around and within the organization. Execution is the implementation of planned planning using the preparations made in the organizational stage (Wibowo, 2006).
- Monitoring or Evaluation: This relates to the learning process involving various factors to achieve the desired goals. Evaluation involves setting standards and ensuring that organizational goals have been achieved. Supervision is closely related to planning so that management effectiveness can be measured (Nanang Fatah, 2001).

In the context of learning Arabic, modern Islamic boarding schools apply the principles of functional and interactional language theory. Functional language theory emphasizes the communicative functions of language rather than language forms, while interactional language theory emphasizes the use of language as a tool for building social relationships. Therefore, learning Arabic in modern Islamic boarding schools focuses on developing students' ability to use Arabic to communicate rather than just mastering language structures (Purwo, 1998).

The principles in implementing Arabic learning strategies include priority, accuracy, stages, motivation, and standard standards. Learning Arabic in modern Islamic boarding schools is centered on developing the ability of students to use Arabic in the context of daily communication under the Islamic boarding school environment that allows them to practice Arabic in real situations (Batmang, 2014).

Learning Arabic in modern Islamic boarding schools takes place in two different environments: formal and informal. The formal language environment involves the learning process in the classroom using structured teaching methods. On the other hand, the informal language environment occurs outside the classroom, where students interact naturally and unplanned in using Arabic in various everyday situations (Batmang, 2014).

2. Research method

The research conducted is a case study type, as explained by Arikunto. The case study is a research method that intensively and deeply explores the symptoms that occur (Suharsimi Arikunto, 2010). In using multi-case case studies, the initial step is to establish the required focus as a definitional boundary, which is also a parameter for other cases, as explained by Bogdan and Biklen :

When researchers study two or more subjects, settings, or depositories of data, they usually do multi-case studies. Case studies take a variety of forms. Some start as a single case only to have the original work serve as the first in a series of studies or as the pilot for a multi-case. Study other studies are primary single case studies but include less intense, less expensive observations at other sites to address the question of generalizability. Other researchers do comparative case studies. Two or more case studies are done and then compared.” (Boogdan, R,C, &S.K, 1998).

After making conceptual discoveries in the two Islamic boarding schools, the next step was to conduct a comparative analysis by developing concepts to gain a more abstract understanding of the Arabic Language Education Program so

that the two Islamic boarding schools could improve their speaking skills. At this stage, a modified analysis is carried out to develop and test a theory (Boogdan, R.C., & S.K., 1998).

The presence of a researcher at the research location still provides several clues, as explained by Bogdan and Taylor in Lexy (Boogdan, R.C., & S.K., 1998) as follows::

- It is important to avoid personally taking things encountered in the field.
- It is best to plan the first visit to meet someone who will introduce the researcher to the research location.
- It is recommended to expect to get less information than possible on the first day at the research site.
- It is best to be passive, show interest, be serious about the research subject, and not ask too many questions that are too specific, especially in potentially controversial areas.
- It is better to maintain a polite and friendly attitude when introduced to people, with a smile and not aggressive behavior, to make it easier for others to accept it (Lexy et al., 2012).

Data are records containing accurate information and are supported by evidence in the field materials used to support research (Lexy Moleong, 2012).

Data can be real physical material that can be analyzed or used as a basis for making conclusions in research.

Data are records containing accurate information supported by evidence in the field and reflect the truth. This data is material used to support research (Lexy et al., 2012). Data can also be real material to be used as a basis for analysis or conclusions in research.

Data analysis aims to identify information related to the results of interviews, notes, or other research materials. This aims to increase the researcher's understanding of the material used in data collection so that researchers can report findings better. By analyzing data, researchers try to organize, detail, synthesize, find patterns, and gain important insights about research subjects. In addition, data analysis also helps researchers prepare information to be conveyed to others (Lexy et al., 2012). In this study, the validity of the data was checked through credibility tests, transferability tests, dependability, and confirmability, according to existing standards (Lexy et al., 2012).

3. Discussion

Learning program planning is the main element in managing educational programs, and after the planning stage, it is followed by the implementation and evaluation stages. This process forms a cycle that runs continuously. As stated by Vincent Gasperz, management is a system that is interrelated to achieve goals by providing services to students and related parties in education (Vincent Gasperz, 2001).

Learning Arabic, which has a deep meaning (meaningful learning), is very important. To achieve this meaningfulness, management is needed by the learning objectives. Learning will be more effective if it has relevance and significance for students. Learning Arabic is a challenging task, especially since Arabic is not the native language in Indonesia. Therefore, good education management is needed in institutions like Islamic boarding schools. Often, problems in learning Arabic arise, such as a mismatch between the material and the methods used in teaching (Tumaji et al., 2018).

Speaking skill, or in Arabic, called "maharah al-kalam," is the ability to express thoughts, ideas, opinions, desires, or feelings through the words and sounds spoken to the other person. Speaking is a very important part of learning a language and is one of the fundamental skills in learning a foreign language. Maharah kalam speaks fluently and continuously without stopping without repeating the same words (Abd. Wahab Rosyidi & Mamlu'atul Ni'mah, 2011).

Speaking ability is one of the most important language skills in learning modern languages, including Arabic. Speaking is the main means of understanding and communicating with other people using language as the medium (Ahmad et al., 2005).

Implementing learning Arabic is a process of interaction between teachers and students/students to convey subject matter and achieve learning objectives. This involves class and student management and organization by the Kyai, including distributing special tasks to teachers. Therefore, implementing learning includes aspects of managing learning in the classroom and managing students (Muh. Khoiril Umam, 2021).

The Miftahul `Ula Islamic Boarding School has the motto "standing above and for all groups," which has been a guideline for students from the start. Although Arabic and English are used in daily communication at the boarding school, there is no attempt to create an Arabic or Western impression in the dress or behavior of the santri. Miftahul `Ula Islamic Boarding School aims to provide religious education to students so that they are ready to contribute to society after leaving the boarding school.

Planning is an important element in achieving educational goals and affects the ability of all components in Islamic boarding schools. In terms of academic and non-academic achievement is the expected result of the planning process. The success and competitiveness of Islamic boarding schools are reflected in the achievements achieved, and good educational management will produce quality results.

4. Conclusion

Planning an Arabic language education program to improve speaking skills at Pondok Modern Al Barokah Nganjuk involves various steps. One of them is preparing qualified teaching staff, which can be achieved through training and further education to increase their professionalism. Within the framework of learning system planning, Pondok Modern Al Barokah Nganjuk has prepared various learning programs consisting of various activities, such as yellow book study, multilingual speech practice, use of Arabic and English in daily activities, and other programs. Learning planning at the Al Barokah Islamic boarding school focuses on the mission of preparing cadres of ulama and community leaders (*mundzirul qoum who mutafaqqih fid dien*) who have professionalism, both as scientists/academics and practitioners and who can carry out the duties of *da'wah ilal khoir, amar ma'ruf nahi munkar, and indzarul qoum*. This will be realized through various activities implemented in an educational program based on "learning by doing."

Suggestions

For the Al Barokah Nganjuk Modern Pondok institution

The results of this study can be used as material for consideration for the leadership of Islamic boarding schools in managing Arabic language education programs to improve speaking skills (*Kalam*) in the modern Islamic boarding school al barokah Nganjuk.

For future researchers

It is hoped that the results of this study can be used as a reference and comparison for carrying out further research, especially research related to the management of Arabic language education programs to improve speaking skills (*kalam*) so that new learning theories and models can be found.

For the UIN Sayyid Ali Rahmatullah Tulungung library

The results of this study are expected to be an additional reference in the field of Arabic language learning programs and variations in the teaching and learning activities process.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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